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The Nation and the Child: Reading R. K. Narayan's *Swami and Friends*

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Abstract:

This paper argues that the idea of the nation is closely connected with the notion of childhood in the context of colonization. Traditionally, childhood was seen as an age of dependence. Through the colonial lens, childhood appeared as a colonized nation and vice versa. R. K. Narayan's *Swami and Friends* (1935) is Narayan's first novel. It is based on his childhood memories, but it is not autobiographical. It shows a child's journey to his dream and an unflinching will to prove himself amidst the reign of dominance, subjugation, rejection, and demoralization. Swami represents the spirit of independence, liberty, and dignity. His participation in the freedom struggle carries historical and symbolic significance. Swami's attempt of revolt is not only for his country but for his freedom too. He reacts against the strong, conservative, and suffocating authority of adults. This novel projects the twin realities of the development of India as a nation and the Indian child. It builds its argument on the relationship shared between an individual and the place and the identity that is derived from it.

Keywords: Childhood, Colonization, Miniature-Adult, Child as Colony, Child Psychology.

Rasipuram Krishnaswami Narayanaswami, famously known as R. K. Narayan, is one of the founding fathers of Indian English Fiction. He is placed among the "Big-Threes" of

Indian English novelists by William Walsh (62). V.S. Naipaul calls him the “Gandhi of Modern Indian Literature” (“The Master of Small Things”). Narayan carved out a place for himself as a regional writer. Like Thomas Hardy’s Wessex, Narayan immortalized Malgudi. He created Malgudi, an imaginary place that could easily be identified with any random place in South India. Like most regional novels, Malgudi narratives carry the themes of conflict between tradition and modernity, urbanity and rustic life, hypocrisy and simplicity. Malgudi transcends regional and physical boundaries. It encapsulates the spirit of changing India despite its imaginary status. It keeps on transforming along with its people, places, and changing generations. Thus, it also shows the topophilia, to use Yi-Fu Tuan and Georges Bachelard concept, “understood as affective, meaning-producing bond between a person and a locale, and emphasizes the importance of creating a strong “sense of place”” (Prieto 60).

Narayan’s first novel, *Swami and Friends* (1935), was published during a challenging phase in his career. In the biography *R.K. Narayan: The Early Years (1906-1945)*, Susan Ram and N. Ram mention the hassles Narayan faced to get his book published by a European publisher. Narayan was so depressed that he even asked his neighbor and friend to throw the manuscript into the River Thames. This friend was Krishna (Kittu) Raghavendra Purna, who was then studying at Oxford (Ram and Ram 143-144). Purna showed the manuscript to Graham Greene. Green went through the script and suggested Narayan abbreviate his name to “R. K. Narayan...because his name sounded difficult for the old ladies in libraries in England to remember, and that is done to increase sales of his books in England” (Bhattacharjee, “A Rare Literary Relationship”). When he reviewed the script of Narayan’s first novel, Greene advised him to change its title from *Swami, the Tate* to *Swami and Friends*. This was easy to remember and matched with Kipling’s *Stalky & Co.* (Ram and Ram 154). The bond of Narayan became so strong with Greene that Ram and Ram wrote the whole biography on their friendship (Subramanian). Narayan acknowledged Greene’s contribution, stating that he “was a big

support for me...editing, titling, and proofing my works besides finding publishers” (Subramanian; Bhattacharjee). The novel was finally published in 1935 by Hamish Hamilton, London. Gradually, Narayan became an established author with his own unique style of writing. Almost fifty years after its publication, *Swami and Friends* was serialized as a part of the Malgudi Days TV serial (1986-7). In 2010, an abridged version of the novel was published by Puffin Books, titled *Malgudi Schooldays*. In 2019, it was included in the BBC's 100 Most Inspiring Novels list.

Swami and Friends draws much of its raw material from Narayan’s life and experience. This becomes apparent in reading his autobiography, *My Days*. Pankaj Mishra writes, the “novel registers all the small confusions and dislocations of the child reaching the end of an idyllic childhood and facing the grave tasks of adulthood” (196). It is the story of a schoolboy, Swami (Swaminathan), and his friends living in Malgudi. It is set in pre-independent India, where the air is rife with the struggle for independence. It was a different period in Indian history, dominated by poverty and illiteracy. Modernization, industrialization, and urbanization were gradually spreading their wings. However, rural and town life remained more or less the same, with changes in surroundings due to modern buildings, railway lines, markets, and machines.

In the introduction to *Malgudi Schooldays* (2010), Shashi Deshpande elaborates that defamiliarization of place also occurs because of time. Place, like all other things, is subject to change. The region and location might remain the same, but they hold a different identity for people from different generations and times. Public schooling was introduced by the British, famously, to train Indians for their colonial project. Describing Narayan’s landscape, Deshpande writes: “it seems almost like a strange country... Schoolboys wore coats and caps to school, sometimes even a dhoti –yes, a dhoti...It was a time when children walked to school, carried ink bottles with them, and money was rupees, annas, and pice” (x). Swami is placed

against this colonial background. Swami's father, Srinivasan, is a typical patriarchal head in the family. Everyone bows to his rule. His mother is a subservient wife. She diligently looks after her family. Though Swami's parents rarely find time for his grandmother, Swami enjoys spending time with her. Later, a baby is born in the family. Swami gradually develops a liking for him. Swami is like any other child in colonial India, devising games and playing with things he has. He enjoys playing with an old cycle wheel.

The colonial notion of childhood differed from the contemporary notion of childhood. It was a period when education was limited to a specific population. Children were burdened with other responsibilities at an early age. They had to share work with their parents. Child marriage was not uncommon. In his study *Child Psychology: Growth Trends in Psychological Adjustments* (2004) George G Thompson observes that children were "viewed as *miniature adults*" and because of this approach "children's behaviour was judged largely by adult standards... This idea about children promoted the adult-centered home where children's wants and needs were subordinated to the comforts of the adult members of the family" (8). A similar revelation resonates in Tagore's words as he writes in *Boyhood Days*: "In our family, those days, the worlds of men and women were poles apart, and so were the worlds of adults and children" (27-28). Thus, the children's world was different from the adult world, and when at times it overlapped, it was because of the education given by parents to children. According to Ashis Nandy in *The Intimate Enemy* (2006), childhood "increasingly looked like a blank slate on which adults must write their moral codes—an inferior version of maturity, less productive and ethical, and badly contaminated by the playful, irresponsible and spontaneous aspects of human nature" (15).

The story deals with Swami's life at home and school, his growth, his actions, and his maturing with age. And the novelist, through various episodes from Swami's life, raises the question of the popular notion of "easiness of childhood." Albert Mission School, where he

studies, is run by Christians. Mentioning the conflict that takes place between Swami and his teacher of scripture, Ebenezar, Narayan shows how the Orient was viewed by the West.

‘Oh, wretched idiots!’ the teacher said, clenching his fists, ‘why do you worship dirty, lifeless, wooden idols and stone images? Can they talk? No. Can they see? No. Can they bless you? No. Can they take you to heaven? No. Why? Because they have no life . . .

‘Did our Jesus go gadding about with dancing girls like your Krishna? Did our Jesus go about stealing butter like that arch-scoundrel Krishna? Did our Jesus practice dark tricks on those around him? (SF 4)

Ebenezar is filled with a superiority complex about his race and origin, and therefore turns blasphemous towards Hinduism. What the teacher is trying to do is well expressed in Macaulay’s words: to create “a class of persons Indian in blood and colour, but English in tastes, in opinions, in morals and in intellect.” On the other hand, the Western knowledge system built on classification and Darwins theory of evolution stretched speciesism to the human world. “Racial classifications... added second-order Darwinism, which seemed to accentuate the “scientific” validity of the division of races into advanced and backward, or European-Aryan and Oriental-African” (Said 206). None in the class had the guts to oppose what the teacher was saying, but Swami did and says: “If he [Jesus] did not, why was he crucified?” (SF 4). He was not ready to accept his teacher’s notion and objected to his words. There are two forms of colonization – one physical and the other psychological. Swami is highly receptive of his teacher’s motives and exemplifies Caliban’s speech to oppose the colonization: “You taught me language; And my profit on’t / Is I know how to curse” (*The Tempest* 18).

Religion has been of prime importance in Indian society. In pre-independent India, religion was a way of living. Religion has been seen as the source, the manner, and the structure

that has ordered almost every field and life itself. When the colonizers came, they attacked religion and made the minds of the natives vulnerable and penetrable with their words. This is shown in Chinua Achebe's *Things Fall Apart* :

The White Man is very clever. He came quietly and peaceably with his religion. We were amused at his foolishness and allowed him to stay. Now he has won our brothers and our clan can no longer act like one. He has put a knife on the things that held us together and we have fallen apart. (183)

Here, the battle is open between the Bible and the Bhagwad Gita. When Ebenezer questions: "Why did they not parry Muhammad's onslaughts?"-he is attacking the firm credence to construct and create space for his faith. Swami is a Brahmin by caste, and he understands well his conventions. He has his Brahmanical notion of God- someone who is divine, beyond human dimensions and limitation, compassionate and immaculate. But Jesus is not like this, and so he retorts: "If he [Jesus] was a god, why did he eat flesh and fish and drink wine?" (SF 4).

The symbols of child training are evident: "school: that dismal yellow building," "the class-teacher", "the headmaster", "the class-room." Class and school turn out to be the symbols of adult encroachment on childhood. It binds a child within its four walls and cages the still undeveloped imagination and unframed liberty of a child. The tight schedule, in addition to the homework that is given, becomes an ever-present nightmare. "Every teacher thought that this was the only subject that the boys had to study" (145). Arithmetic, English, and Geography are present in his mind. "Tables, stool, coat, slate, ink bottle, books- surround him at home. How Swami sees these things is shown by the condition in which they are found: "thrown in a confused heap." When a nation is ruled by an external power, it passes through similar stages of domination and subjugation. "Childhood ... looked like a blank slate on which adults must write their moral codes...it became the responsibility of the adult to 'save' the child" (Nandy 15). The colonizer looked at the colony as an adult would look at a child, who needs to be

trained, taught, and disciplined. In the case of India, whether that be press, law courts, agriculture, or administration, they were so abysmally managed by the British that the natives, like Swami, found themselves “thrown in a confused heap.”

This has colonial connotations whereby a child becomes powerless and dependent while parents acquire the authority to guide and sometimes dominate. E. Ann Kaplan defines this through the concept of ‘imperial gaze’ in *Looking for the Other: Feminism, Film and Imperial Gaze*, which involves the oppressors defining how the oppressed are to be seen, including how they are to see themselves (Waugh 514). This is seen in the chapter, “In Father’s Presence.” Swami’s father’s court was closed, and he began spending the afternoon at home. And father and mother stand together on one side while Swami is made to face criticism. Swami faces continuous scolding and criticism from his father: “How many days is it since you have touched your books?” (SF 96). He questions, “Should I read even when I have no school?” (97). His father incessantly engages in surveillance: “Look at the way you kept your English text, your English text! Are you not ashamed of yourself?... “Look here, boy. I have half a mind to thrash you. What have you in your head? (98, 102). He was confused, as his brain stopped working and thinks: “If one has got to read even during holidays, I don’t see why holidays are given at all? . . . if Father cannot find any work to do, why shouldn’t he go and sleep” (98).

Edward Said writes, “It is natural for men in power to survey from time to time the world with which they must deal” (46). The scale of formulating childhood is tilted more on the penalizing side, creating the fear of pain and getting things done. Father gives Swami a sum to do, but he struggles and fails to answer. “Father seemed to delight in torturing him. How could he know? How could he know what that fool Krishna would pay?” When the sum is finished: “Swaminathan announced at the end of half an hour’s agony: ‘Krishna must pay six annas, and burst into tears” (SF 103). The administration in the hands of colonizers was no different, and that too was inclined to create fear in people and get things done.

K. R. Srinivasa Iyengar reiterates Narayan's remark that Indian fiction was dominated by political themes during its struggle for independence (360). Swami is no less a revolutionary of the freedom struggle. Though he is not the leader of any group, he surely becomes one who supports the cause of independence. Bhagat Singh told to the court when he was on a trial for the Assembly Bomb Case: "By Revolution" we mean that present order of things, which is based on manifest injustice, must change." And in a letter from jail he wrote: "the peasants have to liberate themselves not only from foreign yoke but also from the yoke of landlords and capitalists" (Chandra 254). When Swami hears one such speech, his soul is stirred, and though of tender age, he participates in the bonfire and hartal. This episode is closely built around Narayan's life in 1919 when he was twelve years old. Narayan participated in a march in Madras. His uncle scolded him, stating, "not to take part in politics; all governments were wicked" (Naipaul, "The Master of Small Things"). Narayan gives Swami all the liberty he himself lacked to take his own decisions, and that with an ironic and humorous twist.

Swami transforms into a hero as "he takes a small part in a demonstration for India's freedom, even burns his cap on the bonfire of " foreign" clothes and is expelled from school for his "political" activities" (Deshpande x). He was noticed by school authorities. When he went to school, he was asked for clarification, but again, instead of becoming submissive and delinquent, he accepted the punishment.

[Swami] had unconsciously become defiant and did not care deny the charges . . . Every pore in Swaminathan's body burnt with touch of care. He had a sudden flood of courage, the courage that comes out of desperation. He restrained the tears that were threatening to rush out, jumped down, and, grasping his books, rushed out muttering, 'I don't care your dirty school.'" (SF 125)

This might appear as the foolishness of a child, but then his condemnation of Albert Mission School is indicative of the discarding of Western Education. His step shows that his existence, liberty, and decision-making have to be counted, and they lie at his will, not in the hands of some alien power that is trying to control them.

In a colonized state, the land and the inhabitants are owned by the colonizer. Likewise, Swami's request to his mother and father to give him money to buy his playthings again shows his dependent status. He is completely dependent on them for his expenses. No different was the case with our country when all sources of income and revenues were taken by the British into their hands so that the natives hardly had anything at their disposal.

What becomes evident here is that history and literature are overlapping as disciplines, as forms of writing, and as a fact of life. "The starting point of critical evaluation is the consciousness of what one really is, and is 'knowing thyself' as a product of the historical process to date" (Gramsci 324). Just as a historian cannot escape from his own subjectivity, a writer too cannot escape from the "inventory" of his culture, society, history, polity, and his surroundings. That will also account for reconstructing history from works of fiction and deciphering the colours of imagination in historical texts. Novel shows that "colonial past is not simply a reservoir of 'raw' political experiences and practices to be theorized... (but) it is also the scene of discursive and conceptual activity, characterized by a profusion of thought and writing about cultural and political identities of colonized subjects" (Gandhi 5).

Swami trusted four boys – Somu, Mani, Sankar, and Samuel. Somu, the monitor; Mani, the mighty good-for-nothing; Sankar, the most brilliant boy of the class, and Samuel, who had nothing outstanding about him. Narayan has beautifully portrayed the class scenes when these friends are together- Sometimes silent, sometimes in scuffles, and sometimes in animosity. When a new admission comes into class, named Rajam, he remains almost unwelcome, a fish out of water, but Swami soon befriends him. This severed his relations with other mates, and

he is almost ostracized from the group: "What surprised Swaminathan most was that even genial Somu was grim. Something seemed to be wrong somewhere. Swaminathan assumed an easy tone and shouted, "Boys, what about a little place for me in the game?" Nobody answered this" (SF 34). His friends mocked him as a tail, which hurt him a lot, and he almost felt like weeping. Swami, meanwhile, began to play alone but with an ever-present hankering for his old friends; he wanted to be with them and at the same time was getting detached. The group that had once vivified him now appeared like a phantom to him. He had no courage to face them and find an excuse to escape. On the other side, the bonding between Swami and Rajam strengthened. He began visiting Rajam and playing with him.

Rajam, here is an outsider, superior because of his status and education. Though he never intended to create a chasm between Swami and his friends, that happens. This thing was evident throughout the national struggles; the people who were united earlier were envious of one another because of the British. They saw faith in their colonizer but not in the people with whom they had been for so long. A very common consequence of bitterness between friends is polarization, so that Swami, Somu, and Rajam formed one group and the other comprised Mani, Sankar, and Pea. There occurs a bout between these two groups. The fight that occurs is not a simple result of jealousy but an emotional attachment, a breach of faith, a breakage in the possessiveness of Swami's friends. So was the case with Indian political parties: some in favour of the British, the others against them.

When Swami inaugurates MCC (Malgudi Cricket Club), he needed friends to face the match. Circumstances become such that Swami finds no time for cricket match practice, as the headmaster prevents him from leaving early. He requests his headmaster again and again, but all in vain. His pleas to his headmaster are indicative of India's pleas for freedom. Petition after petition by India was met with proposal after proposal by the British. But none conformed to

the demands of the Indians. Consequently, India launched its Civil Disobedience Movement and Quit India Movement. And here Swami too leaves his school and his house.

Scared of his father and the headmaster, Swami runs away from his home. Outside, he was alone, independent, but the way was horrific, and that scared him. Debilitated due to hunger and fatigue, he swoons. A similar condition was in India when the British asked the Congress to write the constitution for India; there was a sense of insecurity due to the displacement from foreign administration to a native model of governance. Many drafts were written, many hindrances occurred, but ultimately India found its independence on 15th August 1947. And so our Swami too found his home at last. “The energizing feature of this displacement is its capacity to interrogate and subvert the imperial cultural formations” (Ashcroft, Griffiths, and Tiffin 11). The British indulged in the “disciplinary management of natives blends into the rarefied, more exalted image of the Englishmen as producers of the knowledge that empowers them to conquer, appropriate, and manage in the first place” (Vishwanathan 20). An adult is no less; he too epitomizes himself, presents himself as an object of perfection, and at the same time points out the shortcomings of a child. Situating himself at a higher pedestal, he tries to rule a child’s mind by creating an inferiority complex, generating in him a sense of insecurity and helplessness, and an awareness that ultimately he depends on an adult.

Swami and Friends revolves around the conflict between the colonizer and the colonized, and the adult and the child. Swami’s search for identity is governed by the twin realities of his childhood status and the colonized status of his country. He derives his strong sense of place when he faces the criticism of his culture, religion, and people. On the other hand, he is overwhelmed and alienated when he runs away from home. His running away is a dissent from the clutches of his father and school. However, hunger and fear make him realize the importance of home. He returns home, but it is not the same home he had left, nor is he the

same child. His family was worried when he went missing. On his recovery, he transforms into a responsible child who has a greater understanding of things.

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